

TRIGGERS OF VIOLENT STUDENT PROTESTS – A CASE STUDY OF THE UNIVERSITY OF FREE STATE (UFS), SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT: The study comes against the upsurge in violent student protests across universities in South Africa resulting in adverse consequences for both students and institutions. This provides the impetus for this paper, which provide insight into the triggers of violent student protests, from a socio-economic perspective. This study adopted an interpretive paradigm to understand the lived experiences of students who have participated in violent student protests. Theoretically, it drew on emergent norm theory (1993) which provided an understating into collective behaviour changes in crowds due to new behavioural norms in reaction to a precipitating crisis that usually creates solidarity among students. The theory in describes how violence manifests and its consequences for those concerned. The study adopted a qualitative research design, and the sample included students from various political parties and student organisations at the University of Free State (UFS). Data for this study was collected from interviews using an interview schedule. Qualitative analysis was performed using Nvivo12 Pro.

The findings were presented following the research objective that focused on identifying the triggers of violent student protests. The study reveals that the lack of leadership presence

during protests leads to students doing whatever they feel like since there is no guidance or direction from the SRC or student leaders from political parties or student organisations. The lack of response to emails and memorandums sent by students frustrates them, leading to them taking matters into their hands in an attempt to get attention and make those in power attend to them on their issues. The Individual selection of specific student leaders during a protest has the potential to incite violence among fellow protesters. Also, the presence of police and private security on campuses heavily armed with tactical gear causes anxiety among students and is perceived as an act of war.

In conclusion, the study recommends conflict resolution mechanisms, the promotion of non-violent advocacy training and improved communication channels to mitigate violent student protests at higher learning institutions. This paper presents a significant contribution by providing a localised perspective on the cause of violent student protests in South Africa, rooted in comprehensive qualitative research. The use of established theoretical frameworks offers a robust scaffold for analysing protest dynamics. The findings of this paper aim to improve knowledge base and understanding of the nature of violent student protests.

Keywords: *Cost, Higher Learning, Students, Violent Protests, Court Orders*

1. Introduction

This study sought to determine the triggers of violent student protests. Over the past decade, a wave of violent student protests swept across South African universities. It appears that peaceful consultations between students and university management is losing place within South African institutions. The continued occurrence of violent protests (Mokoena, 2014; Oxlund, 2016; Dumako, 2019) and its growing popularity among South African university students (Hall, 2016; Oxlund, 2016) suggests that violence is a pivotal language that individuals within the university management in South Africa easily understand. The peak of the violent protests was in 2016 when students across the country, staged violent protests over free higher education among other things (Hall, 2016), which resulted in a national shutdown of universities. This period was a difficult one for universities as libraries, laboratories and vehicles were torched; artworks were indiscriminately destroyed (Habib, 2018). These actions

reinforced the idea that the use of violent tactics remains most effective for students to engage with university management in the event of disagreements. The remnants of such actions motivate this study as these protests have socio-economic impacts on students and universities.

In March 2021, the Minister of Higher Education, Science and Technology, Dr Blade Nzimande publicised a report which showed the devastating cost impacts of student protests at universities in South Africa. The report indicated that from 2020 to early 2021, South African institutions experienced well over ten violent student protests which amounted to R32791 397.00 of cost maintenance for universities (Mahamba, 2021). The University of the Free State (UFS) encountered a series and consistent annual student protests after the 2016 period. For example, the UFS- QwaQwa Campus reported that on the evening of Monday, 4 April 2022, two buildings were set alight during a protest over NSFAS payments issues (UFS, 2022). The UFS- QwaQwa Campus 2022 student violent protests alone resulted in severe damages to buildings estimated at R35 millions of damage costs. Therefore, research must identify the causes of violent protests; prior writings on student protests have neglected this aspect. The lack of precise documentation and systematic assessment of the triggers of violent student protests at universities offers a basis for this qualitative research study since protests result in damage to universities and bodily injuries to students. This paper is divided into seven sections. Section one introduces the study. Section two deals with the literature review and is followed by the theoretical framework in section three which grounds the study. In addition, section four provides an overview of the methodology used in this research study and section five presents analysis and interpretation of the findings. Lastly, section six focuses on the conclusion and section seven on recommendations.

2. Literature Review

In the last decade students from universities all over the continent have engaged in different forms of violent protests; often using it as a means for goal completion. To put pressure on university management, students from universities have often organised protests against the university authorities. These protests have turned violent, and have led to injuries and threats to life for students and staff of these

universities (Plaut, 2010). While having the ability to lay the foundation for socio-political activism beyond the particular university within which it occurs, student violent protests have also led to the loss of lives, destruction of university properties (Nkosi, 2012); temporary shut-down of the universities or suspension of academic activities (Dumako, 2019), and have an adverse effect on the health, economic and social life of the university community.

2.1 Violent student protests

According to University World News, from 2011 to 2015, South Africa was seen as the protest capital of the world (UWN, 2015). This comes after the rise in student protests during that period, which saw many students take to the streets because of hikes in tuition fees and a lack of transformation in higher education institutions. According to University World News (2015), the biggest highlight of these protests was in 2015, with the start of #RhodesMustFall and #FeesMustFall. This complements the earlier study of Zhao (2003) that in the last decade, students from universities worldwide have engaged in different forms of violent protests, often using it as a means for goal attainment. Some commentators have dubbed the wave of protest sweeping South Africa a revolution by the poor (Lancaster, 2017).

Violent protest behaviour has become like an unstoppable "viral" disease spreading in some university environments (De Vos, 2018). In this context, protest is an expression of anger and a visible display of dissatisfaction (Jay and Templar, 2004:101). Most contemporary studies of social conflict indicate that violent protest is more likely to occur when the group at odds with the institution has had all other forms of expression suppressed when the group is poorly cultured, and when the group cannot trust the management to respond to its demands through non-violent protest or petition (Klaasen, 2020). However, the student's mistrust in the ability of management to deliver on students' grievances carries the risk of increasing violent protests (Mulaudzi and Lancaster, 2017). Protest action is an essential mechanism through which people, especially the underprivileged and vulnerable people acting together, can make their voices heard (Lewis, 2021). Although it is understood that in some cases, the university management does not act on student grievances until a

protest is staged, it remains a sign of weak structures (Iwara, Amaechi, Tshifhumulo and Kilonzo, 2020).

It is essential to accept that protests are disrupting but not always violent. According to Duncan (2016), protests communicate grievances by disrupting existing societal arrangements and bringing problems to society's attention. Violence, by its outset, has trigger points, and so are protests. Porta (2013) believes that violence in protests is a product of aggressive police action. She further states that security services' aggressive policing and suppressive actions can often turn the tide of peaceful protests and prompt violent acts by some protesters. For example, the presence of armed police or security personnel always has an intimidating feature which, by the slightest miscommunication, can lead to confrontations between the students and police. During this analysis, it has become apparent that the justification of aggressive policing is unchallenged by most liberal academics. This behaviour may have reinforced the increased belief that the use of violent strategies remains most effective for students to engage with the university management in the event of disagreements (Iwara, Amaechi, Tshifhumulo and Kilonzo, 2020).

According to Ives and Lewis (2020), protests are more likely to spiral into violence when they are poorly organised. Furthermore, Kiguwa and Ally (2018) submit that well-organised protests with identifiable leadership structures, logical objectives, and members who know one another are better positioned to keep violence-prone actors out of their activities. These factors contribute to the preservation of non-violent protests; as a result, poorly organised protests may be more vulnerable to violence. According to Kendall (2008), some students sometimes take advantage of protests and initiate violence when they see an opportunity to loot. However, at times it is not protesters who engage in criminal activities but rather outside people. While students attend many protests, community members sometimes get involved, mainly if a protest occurs outside the university (Lea, 2013). Individuals join in, and some have bad intentions or see this as an opportunity to commit crimes since it will be difficult to trace anything back to them, unlike students. Protests present opportunities for non-students to loot or do other unlawful acts, primarily career criminals who are always looking for occasions to commit crimes. Therefore, there are instances where

external individuals come in a protest to disrupt and make it uncontrollable. This could be outside individuals joining in and taking part in the protests only to take advantage of or disrupt it (Smit, 2016).

Since protests are inherently disruptive, they can conscientise society about the urgent need for their social problems to be addressed and thus speed up the required social change (Maringira and Gukurume, 2016). For instance, the 2015-2016 protests, because of their disruptive nature across the country raised awareness about the lack of funding for universities and other issues students face. According to Duncan (2016), "disruption is not, by definition, violent" even when protests and demonstrations are held on "private property" (i.e., university campuses). Therefore, the South African Police Service (SAPS) cannot arrest students on charges of "Public violence" and for violations in terms of South Africa's Regulations of Gatherings Act (Duncan, 2016). However, section 17 of the Constitution protects everyone's right to protest peacefully and unarmed. Protests are disruptive if they disturb or interrupt an event, activity or process (Kiguwa and Ally, 2018). The police will always intervene where there is a threat to life and property. For example, interrupting a lecture by entering the venue and shouting or singing may or may not be legally protected, depending on how severe and prolonged the disruption lasts. However, some interruption methods will ordinarily be legally protected. For example, singing outside a lecture hall or silently protesting during a lecture by holding up placards or signs without bringing a stop to the class (Maringira and Gukurume, 2016).

If a protest turns violent and threatens people's well-being, it now involves the intervention of the police to protect university assets and non-protesting individuals. Such conduct justifies the police's intervention depending on the violence's seriousness and length. They often lose their rights to protest as this no longer constitutes peaceful protests (Yabagi, 2017). This right and protection are only lost if those gatherings do not intend to be peaceful. While violent protest is not protected under Section 17, the Constitutional Court has nonetheless found that a protester should be afforded constitutional protection even if there is sporadic violence at the gathering, provided that the individual concerned remains peaceful (Karim and Kruyer, 2017).

Students have also used these disruptive tactics to shut their campuses down until their demands are met. Porta (2013) claims they are two contributing factors to protests being violent: escalating policing and competitive escalation. If the police and private security guards are too quick to use violence – which has often been the case with student protests- these interactions, make the protesters violent. Their actions create what sociologist William Gamson (1985) has called "injustice frames" around the state, where the state comes to be perceived as fundamentally unjust. The sad reality is that the authorities often ignore peaceful, non-disruptive protests. Instead, state repression creates solidarity among protest participants, who then justify the need for violence as a form of self-defence. As Porta (2013) puts it, violence emerges from violence in most cases.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1 Emergent norm theory of Turner and Killian

Turner and Killian (1993) established the emergent norm theory of crowd dynamics to explain crowd behaviour. These scholars state that social behaviour is never entirely predictable, but distinctive patterns may emerge from the crowds if familiar interests draw people together. The Emergent norm theory offers a basis for understanding collective behaviour during protests, especially when students believe they must do something more dramatic to get their point across. The theory suggests that crowds come together because a crisis occurs that forces people to abandon prior conceptions of appropriate behaviour and find new ways of acting, this will further assist in understanding student crowds on how they adjust their behaviour in reaction to the police and university (Turner and Killian, 1972).

The emergent norm theory is often associated with crisis; however, it can be beneficial in certain social situations, especially considering the frequent violent protests yearly. The theory posits that collective behaviour changes in crowds due to the occurrence of new behavioural norms in reaction to a precipitating crisis (Turner and Killian, 1993). That reaction to the situation may include sit-ins, marches, boycotts, and strikes. According to emergent norm theory, people believe there is

strength in numbers. Therefore, they may act together if they see it as the only way to fight those with greater power.

While emergent norm theory was initially applied to various forms of collective behaviour, it is most commonly trusted to help us understand the behaviour of large groups or crowds. For example, student crowds often display violent acts during protests, which the study is keen on identifying the motives behind. In particular, emergent norm theory is applied to understand the behaviour of groups who experience a predicament and are forced to find new ways to respond (Lemonik, 2013). Although not all crowd members may agree, shared definitions and emergent norms rationalise violent action that would not be condoned under normal circumstances. However, no matter how uncontrolled a crowd may appear, norms limit behaviour. In the past, demonstrations that draw much support in numbers have had a better chance of being taken seriously (Kendall, 2008). This resulted in better opportunities for starting negotiations about the matter at hand.

In Addition, the theory states that when people are gathered together in a familiar place or physical locality (like on campus), they tend to act in a manner they would not have if they were acting as individuals. For example, activities such as singing and dancing tend to be done in a group setting to express some desires on the side of students. Turner and Killian (1993) claim that new norms emerge from crowds, and the participants adhere to new norms. The theory further posits that student crowds make their classification of a situation and create norms for conduct that fit the circumstances. Turner and Killian (1993) point out, crowds have at least five kinds of participants:

1. The *ego-involved*; feels personally involved in the event.
2. The *concerned*; also have a personal interest in the event, but less so than the ego-involved.
3. The *insecure*; care little about the matter; they join the crowd because it gives them a sense of power, security, or belonging.

4. The *curious; spectators* also care little about the issue; they are curious about what is happening.

5. The *exploiters*; do not care about the event; they use it for their purposes.

4. Research Methodology

A qualitative research design was adopted for this study as it fits well when a researcher strives to gain knowledge or an understanding of the nature of reality about a social phenomenon. The fundamental goal of a qualitative study is to gather and create knowledge while analysing and understanding human experiences (Neuman, 2014). The study employed a phenomenology research approach. According to Kendall (2008), phenomenology is a wide-ranging form of study where the researcher looks to gather information that explains how individuals experience a phenomenon and how they feel about it. Data collected was analysed using inductive thematic analysis.

The research site for this study was the University of the Free State (UFS) in South Africa. The UFS has three campuses: Bloemfontein, South, and QwaQwa Campus. The Bloemfontein and the South campuses are both located in the city in Bloemfontein, the capital city of the Free State Province in South Africa. Meanwhile, the QwaQwa campus is located in Phuthaditjhaba, a rural area in the Eastern Free State. The QwaQwa campus formerly known as University of QwaQwa (UNIQWA) was an officially a black university mainly for teaching programmers, it was incorporated into the UFS in 2003.

The study employed semi-structured interviews as a method to collect data. Nieuwenhuis (2007) defines an interview as a two-way conversation in which the interviewer asks the participants questions to collect in-depth data and learn about the participants' notions, views, beliefs and actions. The semi-structured interview is best suited for this research approach as it enables flexibility during the interview and can accommodate developing perceptions and notions that the researcher did not think of (De Vos, 2018).

Participants were sampled using primary and qualitative data collection methods. Qualitative research is where a researcher gathers data focusing on in-depth, subjective data that will be analysed to lay bare themes, topics or other patterns for understanding (Kendall, 2008). Furthermore, the study employed a non-probability sampling with a specific focus on snowball sampling techniques. This technique was ideal in this study because it assisted in identifying students on campuses and were directly affected or involved in violent protest. According to Bhardwaj (2019), the snowball process collects samples quickly and is cost-effective. The technique is most appropriate because it follows a referral method where one participant connects to another. Upon identifying and recruiting initial participants, the researcher asks to be referred to other participants who share similar characteristics (Neuman, 2012). Data collection revolves around picking participants through referral until the point of saturation. The target population for this study included student leaders (e.g., executive members of student structures and associations), and student representative council (SRC).

The sample for this study consisted of fifteen participants, from all three campuses cutting across gender, age groups, and level of study. An interview schedule was used as an instrument for data collection. The interview schedule contained questions categorised into participation and experience in violent student protests. The interview schedule is helpful as it ensures that the participant's experience is the same for all respondents during the interview, reducing the risk of bias in the interview process (Bhardwaj, 2019).

Ethical issues were considered in the process of the study. This study followed all the ethical guidelines prescribed by the University of the Free State for dealing with human subjects. The researcher had to apply for ethical clearance from the Faculty of Humanities Scientific Committee and Ethics Committee at the UFS, and the ethical clearance application was approved. Informed consent forms were distributed to the participants ahead of the qualitative data collection. Participants were informed of the purpose of the study and the practice gave participants an option to decide participation. Furthermore, privacy and confidentiality were highly adhered to during and after interviews with participants. Participant's details were not linked to their

responses in the study. In light of this, factious names (Pseudonyms) names were used to reference participants' narratives. The data gathered was strictly used for the research purpose for which it was originally collected. In this study, the interview data were analysed using inductive thematic analysis, through the Nvivo12 Pro software open coding system.

5. Presentation of Findings and Discussions

This section presents and discusses the findings of this study on what triggers violence during student protests.

5.1 Lack of leadership

The findings of this study show that lack of leadership from the SRC or other student organisations during student protests increases the chances of violence occurring. Participants in this study reported that when there are no specific individuals who are leading protests or guiding protesters on what they should do and not, things can get out of order:

There is a lack of coordination and marshalling from the protest organisers because if they are in the protest movement, they also have the emotions same as students are having (Neo).

When students have no leadership on the ground telling them where this is wrong and right, students get to do what they want to do. When we had a protest, we left them to lead themselves at night. In the following morning, windows were broken, fountains kicked, and everything. So, you see a lack of coordination and a lack of a proper plan of action leads to violence (Ithabeleng).

This study finds that disorganisation and lack of control can cause many unintended difficulties for students and the university, as things can get out of control quickly. This finding is consistent with a study by Ives and Lewis (2020), which showed that protests are more likely to spiral into violence when they are disorganised. In addition, Kiguwa and Ally (2018) argue that well-organised protests with identifiable

leadership structures, logical objectives, and members who know one another are better positioned to keep violence-prone actors out of their activities.

5.2 Different agendas

This study found that students participating in student protests often come from different political associations and student organisations as such, their motives for protesting differ according to their affiliations. A view shared by Habib (2018) is that protests become divided by “student leaders’ own complicity in the political agendas of their respective political parties to capture the movement”. Therefore, sometimes there are hidden agendas from certain parties or individuals. Some of these have the potential to derail the purpose and momentum of a protest, as some people may engage in activities that fall outside of the decisions of the collective. The following excerpts demonstrate the frustrations resulting from multiple agendas during protests:

When you have people with different alliances and ways of thinking, that is where you find yourself in violent protests. For example, the last protest was a collective protest decision, but some guys came and burned down facilities. When you burn facilities, the first people they will come for are our student leaders, not random students, but most of the time, the call to destroy facilities does not come from student leaders, it is often just a random person. In some cases, some people join protests to sabotage (Rethabile).

Let me say that a protest can be organised by Democratic Alliance (DA), but someone from the South African Student Congress (SASCO) comes to cause havoc wearing a DA t-shirt because you do not keep tabs on all these members (Neo).

The above interview excerpts further suggest that it is not always the protesters who engage in criminal activities but external individuals who want to use such events to commit transgressions. This resonates with the findings by Kendall (2008), who states that protesters emphasised that other unknown individuals sometimes initiate violence by taking advantage of protests to conduct criminal activities, theft, and looting when the opportunity arises. This indicates an element of sabotage, and student political parties, usually use such occasions to compete for constituents and

increase their party's visibility. Acts of sabotage take place to discredit another political party and their image in the eyes of the students or university management. Something Habib (2018) mentions in his book that "political populism" has often been at play in most violent student protests. As Turner and Killian (1987) point out, crowds have at least five kinds of participants, one being the exploiters. These individuals do not care about the event but use it for their own selfish purposes. This is the category where these individuals would fall into and become separate from the group as they do not conform to the collective views. In addition, the findings of this study indicate that in most cases, those who organise protests end up being responsible for the outcomes of the protests. Unfortunately, this has dire consequences, making them targets to the police or security officials as they become outstanding in the crowd.

5.3 Individual selection

The findings of this study show that during student protests, some student leaders are targeted by the authorities and occasionally get arrested. Participants in this study were of the view that separating and arresting specific student leaders during a protest sparks violence. In addition, the targeting of individuals puts them at risk of being isolated from other protesters leading to cycles of violence.

As leaders within the institution, we have an unfortunate thing that when leading a protest, I am faced with now being identified and being isolated; in a sense to say that when protection services and your police services come, there is already a picture of me circulating throughout the offices to see that this is the individual that is leading the protest (Tsheole).

Porta (2013) noted that violence by its outset has trigger points, and so are protests. This study finds that one of those triggers for protesters is seeing the arrest of one of their comrades. One participant said:

An injustice to one is an injustice to everyone. That is the general way we do things, but now when you have a leader such as the president, and the police are arresting him, after being arrested, students are going to fight (Bonolo).

The study finds that the isolation and arrest of specific student leaders create unity and solidarity amongst protesters, leading to unexpected acts of retaliation against those in charge or law enforcement. According to Steven (2015), calling the police and suspending student leaders does not solve the problem. This further provokes the students and renders the relationship between the police, student leaders and management more conflictual and antagonistic. According to Heerden (2017), it is essential to acknowledge that tensions characterise demonstrations. The police and private security presence in one locality build tension between students and them.

5.4 Police and security presence

The findings of this study show that private security and police presence during a protest causes tensions and difficulties. While the presence of police and security personnel on campus is supposed to assure safety for everyone, the manner in which they conduct themselves can fuel tensions. This study found that police and private security confront students with aggression during protests. As a result, students end up retaliating as a way to protect and defend themselves. Fanon recognises the physical and mental implications of violence. The following interview excerpts illustrate some of the student's experiences in their interactions with police and private security personnel during protests:

In my experience, protests to turn violent because of the deployment of extra security guards from the institution and SAPS personnel. You should remember that when these SAPS personnel arrive at these protests, in most cases, what they do is exert pressure on students to move away. For instance, let us say the students are stopping all operations on campus. In most cases, the SAPS will make sure that they use tear gases and rubber bullets to ensure that students disperse at the point where they are gathering so that on its own leads students to retaliate (Bonolo).

We have seen the level of arrogance that comes from management when it comes to tendencies when students are protesting peacefully, especially at this university. You go and stand by the gate, and then in two minutes, the management calls the police on you. Then, when the police come, they start

shooting at innocent students protesting peacefully, not even armed or carrying a placard. So that is when it turns violent because now students are fighting to defend themselves (Ithabeleng).

The conduct of police and private security has been found to be among the main causes of violence during protests. Kiguwa and Ally (2018) also indicates that the presence of police and private security on campuses during protests and how these groups confront students contribute to turning peaceful marches into violent incidents where university property typically gets damaged. Mbembe (2016) also found that in many protests, students often put up a resistance against heavily armed police leading to disastrous outcomes (Mbembe, 2016). As one participant said:

I have never in my entire existence, while I have been part of these protests, gone to a protest where instantly it was violent. Students are constantly triggered, and unfortunately, they retaliate in that manner, leading to violence (Thelma).

The findings of this study suggest that police and private security presence have a direct impact on the violent behaviour of students. Heleta (2016) found that police presence increases the likelihood of violence during protests, especially when there are weak relations between those in charge and the protesters. According to Dumako (2019), protestors perceive heavily armed police as undesirable and violent actors. In this study, participants indicated that the presence of police and private security on campus indicates management's lack of interest in having a meaningful and peaceful engagement. As one participant put it:

Some few months back when the students protested, they woke up in the morning, the police were there. The police told them they were given the order to remove them. They were not even singing or doing anything. They were sitting on the road, standing still and nothing. So, the police came in and said this was the order they were given. You will be forcefully removed if you do not leave within this time (Rethabile).

Instead of meeting students to hear them out, management opts to send police or security personnel to disperse them (Nkhudiseng).

The participants reported that the police action of coming onto campuses was perceived as an act of the state standing with the university against students. According to Mbembe (2016), deploying heavily armed state police personnel to campuses indicates that the state is protecting the university and its management and sending a clear message to those who threaten it. In addition, Heerden (2017) argues that these interactions between the police and students socialise the protesters into violence in many ways than one. This substantiates the study's findings that participants perceive the deployment of the police and security as a direct attack on them while they are being non-violent.

The heavy presence of security and police gets students at the edge. As you can see, whenever there is a protest, the university organises a security company. You know that company, if we are being honest, that security is the security for a riot. So, whenever they come to students, they are heavily geared for a riot, so obviously, it is going to trigger somebody because I came here peacefully to talk. But, still, you bring me angry people, so I will eventually get angry as well. So, I would say that is pretty much seeing a heavy presence of police. So clearly, you are not willing to listen to us; instead, you want to shut us down (Neo).

The way management communicates with the students is as if we do things peacefully, they do not understand. Clearly, they understand violence because they respond with violence through the police (Rethabile).

Literature shows that the endorsement of police violence against students is detailed as necessary, while the constructs of student violence as part of protests are problematised (Heleta 2016). Students have often had to endure violence in the form of stun grenades, teargas, and rubber bullets during protests. This has meant that by participating in a protest, students face persecution and violent, arbitrary arrests and threats of arrest (Luescher, Loader and Mugume, 2017). In the following interview excerpt, one of the study participants talks about her experience during a confrontation with private security guards who were called on campus to monitor a protest:

The SRC assigned us gates to block before 7 am so that no one can access the campus. The university was so strategic such that by the time we got to campus before 7 am, there were private security guards already in position. So, we thought the main focus would be the main gate. So, when we got to the main gate, as I said, the private security guards were in position, and I closed the gates. The security guards opened it. We closed it again, and then there was someone from protection services, and I cannot remember what happened, but that is when we started fighting. So, I asked him (private security member) "what are you here to do? You do not even study here? I do not know why you are here", and he is like, "no, I have been told to come here", and I am like, "who told you to come here?" So, to us, it is like, the Rectorate can speak to you but not us. So, we wanted a name like someone who deployed a private security company to intimidate us as students. I mean, I believe that it is the university's responsibility to protect us instead of putting security on us (Thelma).

The findings of this study indicate that students are sensitive to the presence of police and private security on campus, which gets them agitated. Additionally, this is predisposed by how law enforcement approaches and the way they treat students during a protest. Although private security companies on campuses are not new, students and security personnel usually have violent clashes during protests. According to Porta (2013), violence emerges from violence. In most circumstances, the police meet resistance with force. This often fosters solidarity among protesters who retaliate and justify using violence as self-defence.

5.5 Retaliation

This study found that the acts of vandalism and destruction of property during protests are attributed to two things: (1) retaliation against acts of violence from the police or private security, (2) it is a way to make the management to listen, and to take notice of students and their grievances. The following interview excerpt gives insight into the experiences of students:

Students vandalise because they are retaliating against the brutality of the SAPS and the security guards that are always present when students want to protest peacefully. Unfortunately, the management deploys these people (private security and SAPS), and it turns ugly. When students retaliate, they destroy things, and the unfortunate part is that every time this occurs, management listens. That is when they open their eyes and want to hear what the real issue are. Therefore, it is a big concern that every time students want to raise their voices that is the approach, they have to take for them to be heard (Nkhudiseng).

Protestors see heavily armed police as proscribed and violent actors (Dumako, 2019). This correlates with the study's findings that seeing police and security personnel on campus during protests further antagonises students as they feel intimidated by their presence. Furthermore, the deployment of security forces (which usually increases further tension in already unpredictable circumstances) to control student protests has been broadly condemned by experts in conflict management (Odebode, 2019). However, the study finds that some participants feel justified with the activities which contribute to the dismantling and burning of university property as they think they are not being listened to from the beginning, and that violent protesting is the only way to get attention from those in charge. Therefore, students believe that through these acts of violence when they get to be listened to:

If you are unwilling to listen to us, the simplest thing is to go for buildings and university property because if we are suffering, you will also suffer. That is what leads to the destruction of property. If you are not willing to sit with us and not have a word with us, okay, we will show you that there is no university without students, so we are prepared to take it down with us. If it persists to that level, you will not listen once, and we do this to make you listen to us twice now (Neo).

The other time earlier this year, students were protesting peacefully on campus; the institution then released a report saying a group of students was running around campus pretending to be protesting. You see, simply because it is not violent. Therefore, it is not a protest, but it is students who are running around

disrupting classes. However, when it starts to become violent, it is a protest. Now, what does that then tell you? So, it tells you that no matter how peaceful you protest, it is not seen as a protest in their eyes; it is seen as students disrupting, but when you start to become violent, you vandalise, you do everything, and then it becomes a protest according to them. Then it brings me back to the saying that our institution or management has become an ancestor. Like an ancestor, you need to burn impepho (incense) first to have your voice heard; the institution as well is like one (incense) where you need to burn something for it to respond. It is therefore worrying and concerning at the same time (Thato).

The above interview excerpts suggest that it is a common belief among students that the management only responds and caters to their needs when they become violent. This belief further encourages students to act violently. However, Holdt (2013) notes that some vice-chancellors refuse to engage with student leaders or do not attend scheduled meetings.

The study finds that the acts of vandalism do not always emanate from police or private security presence and clashes only, but result from the silence of those in charge and their refusal to communicate and engage with students. Violence is necessary, not only to defeat a system of domination, but also to restructure the mind of the colonised subject – specifically to eradicate those feelings of inferiority and fear (Fanon, 2004). Unfortunately, such a response to student demands typically results in students rioting, disturbing classes and causing all sorts of disruptions (Heleta, 2016). According to Iwara et al (2020), the continual manifestation of violent protests and their growing popularity among South African university students suggests that violence is the pivotal language that people within the university administration in South Africa easily understand. One participant said:

When the students have exhausted all possible measures, it is so unfortunate that it even gets to a point where they have to burn; I do not know if you have paid attention to this. You can go now and report an issue; they will not respond. However, when you have decided to go and burn something, that is when they want to come to the ground to talk and negotiate. The question now

is why should there be something that burns for them to come to the ground and listen to the grievances of the students? (Tsheole).

Nowadays, students recognise historically that the oppressor understood violence through violent acts to be heard, valued, and taken seriously to reform and transform the higher education system (Kumalo, 2018). As Fanon (2004) argued, revolutionary violence represents a democratic and more transformative agenda to change relations of inequality, and to configure new interactions between dominant and marginalised members. However, the findings of this study show that although participants admit to the use of burning and vandalism as a tactic to grab the attention of the management, they do not condone those acts themselves as they believe they are not the right things to do but feel like they have no other options:

I do not condone vandalism. We can never condone any form of vandalism or any form of the destruction of property and all that because what that does is that destruction of property takes students twenty steps backwards. However, it is so unfortunate that students have to resort to violent measures for the institution to see that it is necessary to come to the ground (Marvin).

It always must go down to vandalism, and I do not support such, but it has been proven that it is the only way you get the attention of management (Thato).

These acts of violence during protests have dire consequences for students. One of them was the university's closure during protests, which led to delays academic activities and services.

6. Conclusion

The study highlighted important insights regarding triggers of violent student protests. Firstly, it is apparent from the primary data and the literature discussed in this study that violent student protests have been occurring in the past and will still persist into the future. In addition, the literature section discussed nature and causes of violent student protests.

Emergent norm theory provided an understating into collective behaviour changes in crowds due to new behavioural norms in reaction to a precipitating crisis that usually creates solidarity among students. These theories support the study's objectives in describing how violence manifests and its consequences for those concerned. Moreover, the Emergent norm theory focuses on 'crowd behaviour', which believes crowds are normless. Instead, they create norms during protests that fit the current circumstances.

The findings were presented following the research objective that focused on identifying triggers of violence during student protests. The key findings of this study were that the lack of leadership presence during protests leads to students doing whatever they feel like since there is no guidance or direction from the SRC or student leaders from other political parties. Because of this absence, protests are likely to spiral into violence due to the absence of student leaders from the SRC or student associations during protests.

Furthermore, the lack of response to emails and memorandums sent by students frustrates them, leading to them taking matters into their hands in an attempt to get attention and make those in power attend to them their issues. This often leads to students organising themselves to protest. There are individuals from various political organisations with different agendas from these protests. These hidden agendas usually lead to individuals taking advantage of a protest to disrupt or commit misconduct derailing the protest's primary purpose.

The Individual selection of particular student leaders during a protest has the potential to incite violence among fellow protesters. As a result, witnessing the arrest of one of their students results in protesters' retaliation, which unites students. This is related to the finding that the presence of the police and private security during student protests cause anxiety among protesters. The presence of the police and private security personnel on campus is perceived as direct insolence from the University's management to the students because this act of violence occurs as a form of retaliation.

7. Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

7.1 Conflict Resolution Mechanisms

Establish formal structures (e.g., grievance committees, student-staff forums) for timely identification and resolution of student grievances before they escalate. The university management needs to be more understanding in their dealings with the students and understand the political dynamics and power struggles associated with these student structures, which can sometimes make negotiations difficult. This is imperative when it comes to disputes which the university has no control over.

7.2 Promote Non-Violent Advocacy Training

Integrate awareness of peaceful protest, civic engagement, and negotiation skills into student orientation and leadership programs. Student protest leaders need to learn more about their responsibilities and duties when organising protests within the University, especially in line with the protest management policy. Moreover, this includes managing protesting students, so that they do not get violent, even in the face of escalation. Protests are used to communicate a message, especially when university management is not prepared to engage with students equally and transparently.

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